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Multi-scale model to describe the local degradation and mechanical failures in an SOC stack

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Abstract

A multi-physical 3D model of the stack is a useful tool to increase the lifetime of an SOC stack, as this can be used to study the impact of modifying operating parameters, design and/or predict the requirements to the stack component materials. The multi-physics model can estimate the variation of physical quantities (e.g. temperature, overpotentials, thermal stresses), which could be used to assess local degradation or mechanical failures.

Multi-physical 3D models describing all relevant physical phenomena (current, gas flows, heat transport, mass balances and mechanical stresses) with the geometric details are computationally expensive to run, i.e. days on a cluster is required for a single steady-state simulation. However, by using multi-scale models or so-called homogenized models, the computational resources are tremendously decreased, such that a steady-state model can be solved within minutes on a workstation.

A wide range of models have been developed to describe the degradation and failure of cells and other components in the stack for both electrolysis and fuel cell modes of operation. These include Ni migration and agglomeration, Chromium poisoning, corrosion and failure in the oxygen electrode / interconnect interface. Most of these relate simple physical models or empirical models to the observed degradation in actual cells and stacks by fitting a few unknown parameters. These models are rather useful to describe the *local* degradation in SOC stack, but the local evolution will influence the entire stack, and a full 3D stack model is needed to predict the spatial variation of the degradation.

In this paper, we present a 3D model of an SOC stack, where the local degradation and mechanical failures are described everywhere in the stack over the stack lifetime. The model is thus able to describe all relevant physics (currents, gas flows, heat transport, mass balances and mechanical stresses) coupling in space *and* time. Simulations of tens thousands of hours of operation can be computed within an hour or two on a high-end workstation, a task that would have taken months of simulation time with conventional models. This makes it possible to assess the lifetime, effect of design modifications and material requirements for the SOC stack technology.

Figure 1 Temperature of air flow and thermo-mechanical stresses in an SOFC stack simulated by a homogenized model.

Introduction

To increase the lifetime of an SOFC stack testing is eventually a necessity. However, to explore the impact on the degradation of various operating conditions a multi-physical 3D model of the stack is a useful tool. A 3D stack model can be used to study the impact of modifying operating parameters, design and/or predict the requirements to the stack component materials. The multi-physical model can estimate the variation of physical quantities (e.g. temperature, overpotentials, thermal stresses), and with those, it is possible to assess local degradation or mechanical failures.

Multi-physical 3D models describing all relevant physical phenomena (current, gas flows, heat transport, mass balances and mechanical stresses) with the geometric details are computationally expensive to run. For instance, Li, Song and Lin [1] presented a fully-coupled SOFC stacks model made in Ansys-Fluent model of a 30 cell stack with a relatively simple geometry, for which steady-state operation could be simulated in 40 hours on a work station. Similar computational efficiency was achieved in the model by Nishida, Beale and Pharoah [2] using OpenFoam. Thus, if a set of equations from such a stack model should be solved for each time step in a transient model, describing the lifetime of a stack, then the solution time would be at least 500 hours, and thus not practically feasible to use for this type of studies.

In Frandsen, Navasa et al. [3,4] a novel approach for simulating the SOFC stacks were presented, where the multi-physics of an SOFC stack could be simulated in steady-state within 15 minutes using a workstation. To achieve this, so-called homogenization was employed to indirectly include the geometric details of the real stack. By replacing the actual geometry with homogeneous media, with the same physical properties, it is possible to represent the response of the stack. An example of this is shown in Figure 1. The physical properties of the homogeneous media is obtained by extracting the average physical response of the repeating for the different physics [4]. By doing this, the many computational units (finite elements, control volumes, etc.) needed to describe the repeating unit can be replaced by a homogeneous medium. And as it is a homogeneous medium, the discretization can be chosen according to the gradients of the free variables, which is solved for. Thus, Navasa et al. achieved computational time of approximately 15 minutes for a 100 cell stack [4]. With a steady-state solution time of 15 minutes iterative time stepping suddenly appears feasible and thus also the possibility of simulating the degradation over the lifetime of a stack.

Modeling of the SOFC degradation is an important tool for analyzing its long-term performance, investigating effects of the operating and geometric parameters on the lifetime of the SOFC, and so mitigation techniques to improve its lifetime. A limited number of studies have been devoted to numerical modeling of the degradation phenomena of the SOFC. Nakajo et al. [5] integrated degradation phenomena of Ni particle coarsening, Cr poisoning, interconnect oxidation, reduction of the electrolyte conductivity, and formation of insulating phases into a 2D model of a repeating unit of a SOFC stack. Miyoshi et al. [6] applied the Cr poisoning model proposed by Nakajo et al. [5] to a 3D model of the electrodes and electrolyte of a single cell. Moreover, Zhu et al. [7] studied the degradation phenomena of Ni coarsening, electrolyte conductivity reduction, and interconnect corrosion through a 3D model of a single cell. The effects of the model variables such as species concentrations and temperature distribution on the degradation rates over the cell were investigated. Nonetheless, it is obvious that the modeling variables vary over the stack and not all the cells experience the same condition. Therefore, stack-scale modeling of the

degradation phenomena is necessary to investigate the degradation distribution over the stack and analyze the long-term performance of the SOFC stack.

One of the drawbacks of using a homogenized model is that the local parameters like overpotentials, stress intensities at assemblies are not directly obtainable, as the geometric features within a repeating unit and thus the detailed physical response is not directly represented in the model. An analogy to this is that for full cell models, the microstructure of the electrodes is not represented, as the number of computational units would be far too high for current computers. However, the overall response of the homogenized response can be used to achieve the local details in the substructure of the SOC stack again, but so-called localization. In localization, the submodel of the repeating unit is employed with physical parameters (e.g. temperature, currents, flows, stresses, etc.) in a single point in a solution of the homogenized model. The physical parameters at the single point are applied as boundary conditions to the repeating unit submodel and by solving this, the local conditions at the point of interest can be retrieved. With this approach, a multi-scale, multi-physics model can be achieved.

In this paper, an overview of the recent developments of the multi-physics, multi-scale model developed at DTU Energy is presented. These consist of two main contributions, i.e. 1) adding a novel localization approach, which can be used to model the local mechanical failures in the stack using so-called fracture mechanics, 2) making the model transient and able to simulate the degradation of a full-stack in 3D over the full lifetime of a stack (~40,000 hours) in practical feasible time-span, i.e. 1 hour and 15 minutes. The overall approach will be described and examples of results provided.

1. Scientific Approach

The approach in this work is purely modelling. Modelling cannot stand on its own in a true investigation of a phenomenon, but this concerns the development of a new type of models, which will solve a class of problems, which have not been possible until this point, and thus stands for itself. The onwards approach is to ensure that the model provides correct results and work together with SOC stack providers to validate the model for one or more specific stack technologies.

The current stack model relies on homogenization as described in the introduction, and following physical phenomena are simulated in parallel: 1) flow distributions for the fuel and air; 2) turbulent variables for the airflow in the air manifolds; 3) mass transport and electro-chemical reaction of the species; 4) current, voltage, overpotentials, and degradation variables; 5) heat transfer in the solid and fluids; and 6) mechanical stresses in the solids and local energy release rate for fracture in the cell-interconnect interface.

1.1 Modelling localized fractures in SOC stacks

In Navasa et. al. [4]. it was shown how the average stresses could be obtained in the stack based on the temperature profile, thermal expansions and external loadings. Also, it was shown how it would be possible to estimate the stresses in the cell by an analytical model mapping the average stresses to the local stresses in the different cell layers. This was possible because of a simple interconnect geometry for which a simple average stiffness could be deducted.

For more complex interconnect geometries, it is not possible to use an analytical model and the sub-model of the repeating unit must be made numerically. This is certainly also possible and is done e.g. in Refs. [8,9]. In Miao et. al. [8] the effective properties for the homogeneous media are obtained by imposing an increment in the free variable e.g. temperature as boundary conditions to the sub-model and integrating the heat flux, to obtain the heat conductivity.

Figure 2 Concept for retrieval of material parameters for homogeneous media by numerical modelling [8].

The same sub-model used to retrieve the homogeneous parameters can also be used for so-called localization. Once the stack model with homogenization has been run the details in the repeating unit cell geometry is not resolved by the model. For many phenomena, a very high local number of computational elements are needed to resolve for instance variations in overpotentials in the electrodes or stress concentrations at the junction between the cell and interconnect. This can be handled by imposing e.g. the average stress $\bar{\sigma}$ from the homogenized stack model as boundary conditions in the form of tractions (Figure 3b) on the sub-model (Figure 3c).

Figure 3 Concept of the modelling approach, linking the homogenized multiphysics model (homogenized stack model) (a) to the average calculation of stresses (b), which are then connected via a mechanical sub-model (c) to the examination of local fracture energy in the entire stack (d) [8].

To evaluate if a local failure will occur there are two approaches; 1) the statistical approach, where the stresses are evaluated and based on this probability for failure is evaluated (see e.g. [10,11], and 2) the fracture mechanical approach where the Griffith criteria is investigated, i.e. if the energy release rate G for generating a crack is lower than the critical energy release rate (fracture energy) G_c . The latter has primarily been used for the characterization of SOC materials but to the authors' knowledge not been applied in the analysis of SOC stacks.

For both approaches, a consistent set of models and measurements needs to be feasible to evaluate the risk of failure. Whereas, it is less complicated to measure the strength of

bulk materials, the strength of interfaces is difficult to characterize consistently [12]. The reason is that stress across the assembly varies significantly for the different testing methods, and when assuming uniform stress distribution the assumption leads to large variations of apparent strength. Some researchers therefore carefully treat the edges of the specimens used, see e.g. Ref. [13]. However, when producing stacks, the edges of the assemblies are not polished, and the strength measurement will thus result in higher strength than what is reached in practice. A non-conservative approach would be to have samples where a sharp crack is pre-initiated before the mechanical testing.

Thus, for characterizing the mechanical robustness of an interface, we believe that the fracture mechanical approach is more suitable as it is possible to manufacture specimens with the materials and methods used in actual stacking [14,15]. This does however imply that the more advanced fracture mechanical models must be employed in the modelling of the SOC stack. In Miao et al. [8] a simple approach for this was however developed using the sub-model concept. Here, the stresses from the homogenized model are applied as boundary conditions on the sub-model, as described above (Figure 3c). For a certain set of stresses, the stress variation in the repeating unit can be evaluated, and by introducing an initial crack at the critical spot, the local energy release rate G can be evaluated by use of the so-called J -integral [16].

Making this mapping of a certain set of average stresses onto the sub-model to compute the local J -integral can be done easily once, and a sub-routine could easily be set up to evaluate the J -integral for a finite number of points within the SOC stack. However, with this, the computational effort would again increase, although this process could easily be parallelized and solved on a cluster.

In [8], a far more computational efficient scheme is however suggested. In this, the J -integral can be determined by a closed form expression for a 2D loading case (explained in later)

$$J = r_{xx} \bar{\sigma}_{xx} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} + r_{zz} \bar{\sigma}_{zz} \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} + r_{xz} \bar{\sigma}_{xz} \bar{\epsilon}_{xz} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ are average stress and strain components from the homogenized model, and r_{ij} are a set of coefficients, which have been determined using the submodel (as explained in the following). By this approach, it is possible to achieve the J -integral at any point in the stack directly from the average stress and strain field from a simple closed form expression (Figure 3d).

The r_{ij} coefficients are determined by imposing the submodel by each of the fundamental stress conditions as boundary conditions (tractions), i.e. two axial loading conditions (x-direction, z-direction) and a shear loading condition (in xz plane). For each of the fundamental stress condition, the J -integral is evaluated by solving the finite element problem for the numerical sub-model (Figure 4a) and consequently evaluating the J -integral (Figure 4b). As no other loads are imposed on the sub-model, only one of the terms of Eq. (1) remains, and the relevant r_{ij} coefficient can now be obtained as it is the only unknown in Eq. (1). It is also shown in [8] that Eq. (1) applies to any combination of the fundamental stress conditions, why their contributions to J can be determined for any given combination.

Figure 4 a) Stresses on sub-model of the repeating unit and b) path for the J-integral.

1.2 Modelling degradation in an SOFC stack

As mentioned in the introduction, the main challenge of describing the degradation over time of an SOFC stack is the lack of computational resources for the conventional stacks. Using a homogenized stack model, the computational needs are far more moderate, making this possible.

Making the homogenized stack model transient was done in Rizvandi et al. [17], but the stack model was also improved by introducing manifolds in the stack and using a more effective computational scheme.

Setting up the model to be transient is possible within the Comsol Multiphysics environment since the standard partial differential equations (PDEs) with a transient version of them were used throughout the model framework. Only material parameters relating to the time dependency of the PDEs, such as heat capacity of the different structural components is needed to make the model transient. However, because of the slow degradation, phenomena such as double layer capacitance and other sub-second time-dependent responses of the cell can be neglected.

The integration of manifolds to the homogenized stack model was also done in Rizvandi et al [17]. The free flow in the manifolds was described by a separate PDE, i.e. Navier-Stokes equations. Because of the turbulent flows in the air flow manifolds, Reynold's average Navier-Stokes (RANS) was used to describe the turbulent flow in them. Specifically, the $k-\omega$ turbulence model with Wilcox's revised formulations [18] was used.

The current model is not specific towards a specific stack or cell technology, but is rather demonstrating what is now computationally feasible. Therefore, degradation models for the most common degradation mechanisms are implemented in the stack model, but with the origin from various groups on and various materials. The degradation phenomena considered in the stack model and the models used are:

- nickel coarsening in the fuel electrode [19],
- chromium poisoning of the oxygen electrode [6],
- and oxidation of the interconnect [20].

With respect to the oxidation of the interconnect, also the threshold for break-away oxidation was added to the model.

The computational efficiency of the stack model was further optimized by careful meshing, simulating only half the stack (symmetry) and by tuning the segregated solution approach in Comsol Multiphysics in Ref. [18]. Hereby the computational time of the full stack model with all the physics present including turbulent flows in the manifolds, but except from solid mechanics, could be brought down 5 minutes for a steady-state simulation on a high-end workstation (Intel Core i9 3.5 GHz 12-core processor, 128 Gb ram). Solving the same model transiently over 38,000 hours including degradation takes 1 hour and 15 minutes.

2. Simulations and results

The simulations were done on a stack operating with co-flow. The co-flow was established by having two external air manifolds, one at each end of the stack in the flow direction, and two external fuel manifolds to either side of the stack to distribute the flow across the stack before it enters the flow direction.

A stack of 100 cell was chosen for this example with an overall stack geometry as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Schematics and overall geometry of the simulated stack [8].

Pressure boundary conditions were set to supply the flows of air and hydrogen with a pressure difference of 8 and 0.4 mbar, respectively. The current was adapted to the resulting flows to have a fuel utilization of approximately 70 %. The inlet temperature was 700°C and the load current was 25 A for the 10x10 cm² active area stack (0.25 A/cm² average current density).

2.1 Local fractures in an SOFC stacks

In Figure 6 an example of simulations with the stack model, analysing the average stresses based on the temperature distribution and using these to determine the local energy release rate, using the J-integral approach described in Section 1.1. It is seen that due to the relatively non-uniform hydrogen fuel distribution the current density and temperature distributions become non-uniform. This results in high vertical tensile stresses at the air inlet. These high vertical stresses results in corresponding high values for the J-integral, which would most likely induce failure (depending on the material toughness).

Figure 6 Examples of output from the stack model: a) Temperature distribution, b) Current density distribution, c) average vertical stress distribution, and d) local critical energy release rate for a crack between the oxygen electrode and interconnect.

2.2 Degradation in an SOFC stack

Figure 7 shows the evolutions of the spatial distribution of the area specific resistance (ASR) and the resulting current density distribution. Again, the impact from the uneven fuel flow and temperature distribution is seen to impact the distribution of degradation across the stack. After 37,000 hours, the simulation shows that, with the chosen geometry and operating temperature, it is Cr-poisoning of the air electrode, which increases the activation overpotential dramatically, resulting in a high ASR at the inlet, see Figure 7b". For more details on the evolutions of the various overpotentials across the stack, please refer to [17].

Figure 7: Evolutions of spatial distributions of (a, a', and a'') current density and (b, b', and b'') ASR over the stack.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, it is shown how different model developments now make it feasible to simulate for *full* SOC stack: 1) very detailed local failures, 2) degradation over the lifetime of a stack.

It is made possible by using the so-called homogenization approach, which reduced the steady-state simulation time from ~40 hours to 5 minutes for a full stack with all relevant physical phenomena. This makes the transient simulations of a full stack possible. Using state-of-the-art degradation models from the literature it is possible to simulate the degradation in a full stack over the lifetime of 37,600 hours of operation within 1 hour and 15 minutes. With this computation speed, it is possible to explore a high number of operating scenarios, but also look into the effect of dynamic operation (future work).

The drawback of the homogenization approach is that local details are not described directly, as e.g. the local stresses at the interface between the oxygen electrode and the interconnect. This was however made possible by introducing a simple function, which is used to map the available average stresses to the local so-called J-integral, with a swiftly evaluated closed form expression. The J-integral is a way to evaluate how much energy will be released by crack growth, which can be compared to the critical energy release rate

measured in experiments. This is thus a fracture mechanical approach, which in the authors opinion contemplate a more solid approach to analysing interfacial fractures, as interface strength measurements are hard to do right.

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